

Bachelor's Degree in Computer Engineering

EI1039 – Software Design

SEMINAR 1

Introduction to Prompt Engineering Workshop

Objectives:

1. Introduce prompt engineering and learning strategies to effectively interact with generative AI (GenAI) tools.
2. Train to design structured, contextual prompts to handle complex tasks.

Working Methodology

1. Review and discuss with the class the materials of the UJI's training course "*Introduction to generative artificial intelligences. Gemini, ChatGPT and others*" (Spanish):

- a. [Introduction](#)
- b. [Gemini](#)
- c. [Prompt usage](#)

2. Read "[How do you teach computer science in the A.I era?](#)". Discuss with the class the following paragraph:

*"The future of computer science education, Dr. Maher said, is likely to **focus less on coding and more on computational thinking and A.I. literacy**. Computational thinking involves breaking down problems into smaller tasks, developing step-by-step solutions and using data to reach evidence-based conclusions."*

3. Read "[Coding is dead: UW \(University of Washington\) computer science program rethinks curriculum for the AI era](#)" and discuss the following topics:

- a. If AI tools can increasingly generate code from high-level descriptions, what do you think will become the most important skills for software developers, and why?
- b. How should university courses change to balance teaching core computing fundamentals while also incorporating AI tools into everyday learning?
- c. What abilities or mindsets should students develop today to remain valuable in a future where AI handles much of the routine programming work?

4. Read "[How to turn ChatGPT in the perfect assistant](#)" (Spanish) and discuss the keys of a good prompt:
 - a. Be detailed, concise and with context: [role] [task] [context] [format] [style]
 - b. Provide examples of the required output so the GenAI can follow a structure or style.
5. Read "[How people are using ChatGPT](#)" and discuss:
 - a. Given that AI is primarily used for asking (advice), doing (task execution) or expressing (reflection and exploration), how software developers can exploit these patterns of use?
6. Read "[GPTs and Hallucination](#)" and discuss the following topics:
 - a. Why might a language model generate answers that sound correct but are actually wrong, and what does this reveal about how these systems work?
 - b. Why do you think AI systems perform better on well-known topics than on niche or controversial ones, and how does the training data influence this?
 - c. Given these limitations, how should developers and users approach AI-generated outputs, especially when accuracy is critical?